

Specifying main characteristics of five Iranian local cultivars of almond (*Prunus dulcis* Mill.)

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For introducing five Iranian local cultivars of almond *Sahand*, *Shokufe*, *Azer*, *Yalda* and *Monagga*, a primary study was carried out on some major characteristics of them. *Sahand* cv. with 9100 G.D.H. (Growth Degree Hours) heating and 384 C.U. (Chilling Unit) chilling requirements operated as the latest bloom (middle April). Also, *Shokufe* cv. as earlier ripen (late August), *Azer* cv. as more productive (654 kg/h kernel) and easier harvest and *Monagga* cv. as earlier bloom (middle March) were specified in this study. Variance analysis of kernel and shell dimension and weight, the ratio of kernel/shell weight, number of spurs on branches and flower bud number in spurs showed the significant differences among cultivars ($P \leq 5\%$) whereas differences in amount of carbohydrates, proteins and lipids of kernels were non-significant.

Keywords: Almond cultivars, chilling, heating, spur, kernel, shell

INTRODUCTION

Based on the statistics of F.A.O organization (<http://www.fao.org/faostat>), Iran produces about 110,000 t/year almond crops in over 172,000 h areas and in this respect is the fourth country in the world (figure 1).

Almond is one of the oldest crops in Iran and this country with its nearby regions are counted as diversity and development centers for different almond species (Ladinsky, 1999; Gahraman, 2002; Chaichi, 2005). Regarding to this matter, studying and selecting promising genotypes among native almond population has been followed in the national breeding program of almond in Iran from fifty years ago.

1986), Alnem 1, Alnem 88, Alnem 201, etc. (Kochban and Spiegel-Roy, 1976) have already been introduced in the world but some of them are not adapted perfectly with Iran's conditions. On the other hand, at present many local cultivars have been planted in extensive areas of different regions of Iran that mostly are early bloom and so lose all or portion of their crop due to late frost damage. Therefore, investigations to obtaining new superior cultivars with mentioned characteristics above have been followed continuously up to now.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out on five local cultivars of almond named; *Sahand*, *Shokufe*, *Yalda*, *Azer*, *Monagga* and *Nonpareil* cv. (as control) at the *Sahand horticultural research station* located in 25 km of southwest of Tabriz with 37°55' latitude, 45°57' longitude and 1350 m altitude. The studied characteristics included; full blooming date, easy harvesting, the spur numbers on each meter of yielded branches, flower bud number in each spur, ripening date, tree chilling requirement, location of flower buds, heat requirement for opening flower buds, suitable pollenizer, vigor and form of tree, shell softness, shell and kernel dimensions and weights, double kernel percentage, the ratio of kernel/shell weights and the amount of lipids, proteins and carbohydrates of kernels. The characteristics of shell softness, tree form and vigor, easy harvesting were ranked according to *I.B.P.G.R.* (*International board for plant resources*) descriptors, tree chilling and heating requirements with *Spark* method (Spark, 1993) and others were recorded based on statistical methods.

Fig. 1. Iran's share of global production of almond

The main aims of this program are achievement to high productivity, high kernel quality, shell softness, late blooming date and toleration against environmental stresses. Although, many commercial cultivars of almond including: Texas, Ferragnes, Nonpareil, Marcona, Masbouvera, etc. (Westwood, 2009) and tolerant rootstocks such as GF677, GF557, Hansen 536, Hansen 2168 (Kester and Asay,

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tables 1 and 2 show the results of recorded attributes in relation with tree and fruit of studied almond cultivars respectively. *Sahand* cv. was later bloom than others (middle April) and so produced economic crop under late spring frost conditions. Also, recording chilling and heating requirements of each cultivar showed this cultivar had the highest rate of both kinds. Although, *Shokufe* cv. had 200 C.U. chilling and 5700 G.D.H. heating requirements respectively and it seemed to be an

early or middle bloom cultivar, but it operated as a late bloom. That might be resulted from the slow temp reaction of flower buds or late beginning of physiological dormancy and or both of them. However, *Monagga* cv. as a typical early bloom cultivar had less dormancy period than other cultivars conformity with its low chilling requirement. Also, was not observed significant differences among the full blooming date of *Yalda*, *Azer* and *Nonpareil* cvs. and the flowers of them were opened almost in the same time (early April).

Table 1. Tree characteristics of five Iranian local almond cultivars

Characteristics	Cultivars					
	<i>Sahand</i>	<i>Yalda</i>	<i>Shokufe</i>	<i>Azer</i>	<i>Monagga</i>	<i>Nonpareil (Cont.)</i>
Full blooming date	Middle April	Early April	Middle April	Early April	Middle March	Early April
Ripening date	Middle September	Middle September	Late August	Early September	Late August	Late August
Easy harvesting	Intermediate	Relatively low	Low	Relatively high	Intermediate	Intermediate
Tree vigor & form	Strong, Upright	Strong, Spreading	Strong, Spreading	Intermediate, Spreading	Intermediate, Spreading	Intermediate, Spreading
Pollenizer	Ferragnes, Shokufe	Azer	Ferragnes, Sahand	Nonpareil, Shokufe	Mamae, Sefid	Yalda, Azer
Location of flower buds	Mostly on spurs	Mixed	Mostly on shoots	Mixed	Mixed	Mostly on shoots
Flower bud number in spur	4.60 a	3.99 ab	2.58 c	3.70 ab	3.60 b	3.55 b
Spur number on branch	46.34 a	37.92 ab	25.67 b	38.50 a	40.33 a	31.01 b
Chilling req. (C.U)	384	220	200	329	50	300
Heating req.(G.D.H)	9100	5700	5700	6500	5800	7300

Table 2. Fruit characteristics of five Iranian local almond cultivars

Characteristics	Cultivars						
	<i>Sahand</i>	<i>Yalda</i>	<i>Shokufe</i>	<i>Azer</i>	<i>Monagga</i>	<i>Nonpareil (Cont.)</i>	
Shell softness	Hard	Soft	Soft	Intermediate	Soft	Soft	
Shell dimension (mm)	Length	24.2	18.3	17.8	20.0	18.1	17.7
	Width	35.0	36.9	25.4	28.7	28.6	32.0
Shell weight (g)	4.25	1.96	1.32	2.51	1.64	1.62	
Kernel dimension (mm)	Length	24.2	27.8	20.0	23.2	22.2	25.0
	Width	15.5	11.2	11.0	13.2	12.1	12.2
	Thickness	7.80	7.20	7.65	8.42	8.54	7.55
Kernel weight (g)	1.18 a	1.07ab	0.78 b	1.01 ab	0.98 b	1.12 a	
Kernel /Shell (%)	27	55	58	43	60	68	
Double kernels (%)	16	3	-	4	2	10	
Lipids (%)	51.9	52.4	58.2	60.1	56.7	53.8	
Proteins (%)	21.9	20.8	22.5	20.1	20.2	18.9	
Carbohydrates (%)	19.8	20.1	19.2	19.6	20.7	20.4	

Fig. 2. Yielding rate of Iranian almond cultivars.

Pull off force of fruits was recorded for evaluation of easy harvesting and results showed that *Azer* cv. with -11.2 N harvested easier whereas *Shokufe* cv. with -22.6 N was harder from this viewpoint. This parameter may be important for adjustment of shakers in mechanical harvesting.

So, as the studied cultivars were incompatible, it became necessary to determinate some suitable pollenizers for them. It was carried out after isolation of at least 500 flower buds from each one and inoculation of them with some cultivars pollen. In this way, the best compatible pollen was specified by counting formed fruits at the end of season.

All experimental trees have been grafted on native almond seedlings and it may be considerable about obtained data for the characteristic of tree vigor and form. Also, statistical analysis of spur number on branches, flower bud number in each spur, shell and kernel sizes and their weights showed the significant differences among cultivars at 5% probability level (tables 1, 2). However, differences among cultivars were not significant in relation with the amount of lipids, proteins and carbohydrates of kernels.

The comparison of studied cultivars performance with *Nonpareil* cv. revealed that they could be to use for commercial aims. The difference of yielding rate (kernel) of *Azer* and *Yalda* cvs. with control was non-significant (figure 2). Although, *Sahand* cv. produced lower kernel but based on regional observations, it had the best

acclimation with Azerbaijan conditions and its toleration against late frost damage and stable productivity generally compensated differences of yielding.

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İranın Beş Yerli Badam (*Prunus dulcis* Mill.) Sortunun Əsas Xüsusiyyətlərinin Müəyyənlişdirməsi

Xulasə

Tədqiqatlar İranın *Səhənd*, *Azər*, *Şukufə*, *Yəlda* və *Monəqqə* adlı beş yerli badam sortlarının istehsala buraxılması üçün onların əsas xüsusiyyətləri üzərində aparılmışdır. Əldə edilmiş nəticələrə əsasən, *Səhənd* sortu 9100 G.D.H (İnkişaf dərəcəsi saati) istilik və 384 C.U (soyuqluq vahidi) soyuqluq tələb etməklə özünü ən gec çiçəkləyən (Aprelin ortasında) sort kimi göstərmişdir. Həmçinin *Şukufə* sortu ən tez yetişən sort (Avqustun sonunda), *Azər* sortu məhsuldar (654 kq/ha) və asan yığılan sort və *Monəqqə* sortu ən tez çiçəkləyən sort (Martın ortasında) kimi göstərilmişdir. Hesablanmış variasiyaların analizinə görə, qeyd olunan sortların arasında dənə və çəyirdəyin ölçüsü və çəkisi, budaqların üzərindəki tumurcuq, habelə onların içində yerləşən çiçək gönçələrinin sayı kifayət gədən fərqli olmuşdur ($p \leq 0.05$). Lakin, dənədə karbohidratların, zülalların və lipidlərin orta qiymətlərinin arasında ciddi fərq görünməmişdir.

Определение Основных Особностей Пяти Иранских Местных Сорта Миндаля (*Prunus Dulcis* Mill.)

Исследования были проведены на основе основных особенностей пяти иранских местных сортов миндаля Саханд, Шукуфе, Азер, Ялда и Монагга для выпуска на производство. Основываясь на полученные результаты сорт Саханд с 9100 G.D.H. (часы степени роста) к теплу и 384 C.U (показатель холода единица охлаждения) к холоду требовательный показал себя как сорт с самым поздним цветением (в середине апреля). Кроме того, сорт Шукуфе показан как самый ранозревающий (в конце августа), сорт Азер как продуктивный (654 кг/ч ядра) и легко собираемый и сорт Монагга как самый раноцветущий (в середине марта). По анализу рассчитанных вариаций размер и масса семени и косточки, соотношение веса семени / косточки, число расположенных на ветках почек и число цветочных бутонов в почках среди указанных сортов оказались достаточно различными ($P \leq 5\%$), в то время как различия в количестве углеводов, белков и липидов в семени были незначительным.